

A New Synthesis of (9Z,12E)-9,12-Tetradecadien-1-yl Acetate

SANJIV SHARMA, ARUN SABHARWAL, VIJAY DOGRA, O. P. VIG and G. L. KAD*

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh-160 014

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Synthesis of (9Z,12E)-9,12-tetradecadien-1-yl acetate, the sex pheromone of almond moth, *Cadra cautella* (Walker) and Indian meal moth, *Plodia interpunctella* (Hubner) has been synthesised via Li_2CuCl_4 catalysed coupling reaction.

(9Z,12E)-9,12-Tetradecadien-1-yl acetate (1) is the sex pheromone of the almond moth, *Cadra cautella* (Walker)¹, Indian meal moth, *Plodia interpunctella*², *Anagasta kuhntella*³ and *Spodoptera exigua*⁴ and one component of the sex pheromones of *Ephestia elutella*⁵, *Spodoptera eridania*⁶ and *Spodoptera litura*⁷. Literature⁸⁻¹³ records a few syntheses of 1 in most of which several steps are involved and overall yields are not always satisfactory. In continuation of our interests¹⁴⁻¹⁷ in the synthesis of sex pheromones, we report a simple and unambiguous synthesis of (9Z,12E)-9,12-tetradecadien-1-yl acetate (1) in good yield.

Alkylation¹⁸ of tetrahydrofurfuryl chloride with 1-bromo-2(E)-butene in $\text{Li}/\text{Li}_q\text{NH}_3$ using Fe^{III} as catalyst afforded 7(E)-nonen-4-yn-1-ol (2) in 60% yield. Hydrogenation of 2 in hexane using Lindlar's catalyst and a few drops of pyridine gave (4Z,7E)-4,7 nonadien-1-ol (3) which on treatment with PBr_5/Py furnished 4 in 69.7% yield. Coupling¹⁹ reaction of 4 with 1-tetrahydropyranyloxypentyl magnesium bromide in anhydrous THF using Li_2CuCl_4 as a catalyst at -10° yielded 1-tetrahydropyranyloxy-(9Z,12E)-9,12-tetradecadiene (5) which was acetylated with AcCl/AcOH mixture containing small amount of pyridine to give the desired pure pheromone (1) after chromatographic purification in 79.3% yield and 15% overall yield. Spectral data of the compound (1) were found to be consistent with that reported in the literature⁸⁻¹³.

Experimental

Tlc was performed using silica gel-G (N.C.L., Poona) impregnated with plaster of paris (13%) and column chromatography using silica gel (200-100 mesh; Acme). Ir spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and ^1H nmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal reference. The elemental analysis was carried out at R.S.I.C.,

Scheme 1

Panjab University. The organic extracts were dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 .

7(E)-Nonen-4-yn-1-ol (2). To a well-stirred solution of lithium amide (prepared from Li 2.1 g, 300 mmol) in liquid ammonia (1 dm³) was added tetrahydrofurfuryl chloride (12.0 g, 100 mmol) in THF (20 ml) during 15 min and stirred further for 3 h. To the resulting solution was added 1-bromo-2(E)-butene (13.5 g, 100 mmol) in THF (25 ml) during 30 min. After stirring further for 3 h, the reaction mixture was quenched with saturated solution of NH_4Cl , extracted with ether (4 x 50 ml) and the ether extract dried. Evaporation of the solvent followed by column chromatography using petroleum ether-ether (9:1) afforded 2 (8.2 g, 60%). (Found: C, 78.12; H, 10.02. $\text{C}_9\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ requires: C, 78.26; H, 10.14%); ν_{max} (neat) 3600-3300, 2190, 1650 and 970 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(\text{CCl}_4)$ 5.4-5.6 (2H, m), 3.2-3.6 (3H, m), 1.7-2.2 (7H, m) and 1.0 (2H, m).

(4Z,7E)-4,7-Nonadien-1-ol (3): 2 (5 g, 30 mmol) was hydrogenated in the presence of 1% Lindlar's catalyst (0.350 g) and pyridine (2 drops). When

one equivalent of hydrogen was taken up, the catalyst was filtered off, the filtrate successively washed with dilute acetic acid, water, aqueous sodium bicarbonate and water and dried. Solvent removal followed by column chromatography using petroleum ether-ether (9:1) gave 3 (3.98 g, 79.6%) (Found: C, 77.02, H, 11.25. $C_9H_{16}O$ requires: C, 77.14; H, 11.42%); ν_{max} (neat) 3600-3400, 2940, 1650, 960 and 720 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(CCl_4)$ 5.4-5.8 (4H, m), 3.3 (3H, m), 1.8-2.2 (7H, m) and 1.0 (2H, m).

(4Z,7E)-4,7-Nonadien-1-yl bromide (4): To a well-cooled and stirred solution of 3 (7.0 g, 50 mmol) in dry ether (100 ml) containing a small amount of pyridine, was added PBr_3 (6.75 g, 25 mmol) in dry ether (15 ml) dropwise. The reaction mixture was left overnight, refluxed for 2 h, cooled, poured into ice-water and extracted with ether (3x50 ml). The ether extract was washed with 10% aqueous $NaHCO_3$, brine and dried. Evaporation of solvent furnished 4 (7.06 g, 69.7%) which was used as such for the next operation. Its ir spectrum did not show any absorption in the hydroxyl region; $\delta(CCl_4)$ 5.3-5.6 (4H, m), 3.5 (2H, t, J 6 Hz), 1.7-2.1 (7H, m) and 1.0 (2H, m).

1-Tetrahydropyranyloxy-(9Z,12E)-9,12-tetradecadiene (5): To the Grignard reagent - prepared from 1-tetrahydropyranyloxyethyl bromide (2.51 g, 100 mmol) and activated Mg turnings (0.24 g, 100 mmol) in anhydrous THF (20 ml) under nitrogen atmosphere - was added the bromide (4; 2.03 g, 100 mmol) in anhydrous THF (10 ml) dropwise at -10° and stirred for 30 min. To the resulting mixture a catalytic amount of Li_2CuCl_4 (1.5 ml) was added and stirred further for 5 h at -10° . The reaction mixture was quenched with saturated solution of NH_4Cl (20 ml) and extracted with ether (4x50 ml). The ether extract was washed with brine and dried. Removal of the solvent followed by column chromatography employing petroleum ether-ether (9:1) as eluent gave 5 (2.2 g, 75.2%) (Found: C, 77.32; H, 11.37. $C_{19}H_{34}O_2$ requires: C, 77.55; H, 11.56%); ν_{max} (neat) 2950, 1640, 1470, 970 and 730 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(CCl_4)$ 5.5-5.8 (4H, m), 4.5 (1H, s), 3.3-3.6 (4H, m), 1.8-2.2 (7H, m) and 1.0-1.6 (18H, m).

(9Z,12E)-9,12-Tetradecadien-1-yl acetate (1): A mixture of acetyl chloride (0.8 ml, 10 mmol), acetic acid (2 ml, 36 mmol) and pyridine (0.8 ml, 9 mmol) was added to 5 (1 g, 3 mmol) at 0° dropwise during

1 h and stirred further for 12 h at room temperature. The reaction mixture was then decomposed with cold water and extracted with ether (3x50 ml). The ether extract was washed with 5% $NaHCO_3$ and dried. The solvent was removed and the resulting residue was chromatographed using petroleum ether-ether (9:1) to give 1 (0.67 g, 79.3%) (Found: C, 76.03; H, 10.96. $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$ requires: C, 76.19; H, 11.11%); ν_{max} (neat) 2950, 1730, 1650, 970 and 730 cm^{-1} ; $\delta(CCl_4)$ 5.4-5.6 (4H, m), 4.1 (2H, t, J 6 Hz), 1.7-2.2 (10H, m), 1.0-1.5 (12H, m).

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